

BEYOND THE TEXTBOOK: EXPLORING THE EFFECTS OF MOZABOOK'S 3D SCENES ON READING INSTRUCTION IN THE EFL CLASSROOM

Yanbastieva-Petrova L.

PhD Candidate

Department of English Studies, Faculty of Humanities

Konstantin Preslavsky University of Shumen, Bulgaria

Head Teacher of English as a Foreign Language

Yoan Ekzarh Balgarski Secondary School, Shumen, Bulgaria

ORCID: 0000-0002-1887-5943

Abstract

Developing reading skills has always been regarded as a foundation of both academic achievement and personal growth. However, with the advancement of technology, there has been a change in the way people engage with information – it is frequently perceived visually and audibly rather than through written texts. Young people's reading and learning habits have changed and they often consider studying from traditional paper textbooks as something old-fashioned and boring. Therefore, teachers should meaningfully integrate digital resources and interactive technologies in lessons in order to engage their students' attention and to equip them with the necessary literacy and digital literacy skills. This study explores the potential of 3D scenes as a tool for enhancing reading skills and language comprehension in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. Conducted with 8th-grade students (A2-B1 proficiency level), the research integrates interactive 3D scenes, such as a virtual exploration of Stonehenge, into reading-focused lessons. The methodology combines immersive technology with traditional reading tasks, encouraging engagement and contextual understanding. Data collected through a questionnaire reveal students' attitudes toward 3D-enhanced learning, highlighting its benefits in vocabulary acquisition, contextual comprehension, and overall motivation. Findings suggest that 3D scenes create an immersive learning environment that bridges visual and textual content, offering a dynamic approach to language education.

Keywords: reading skills, digital literacy, EFL teaching, mozaBook.

Introduction

Developing reading skills to a certain level of proficiency has always been regarded as a foundation of both academic achievement and personal growth. For language instructors and learners alike, being a fluent reader guarantees not only academic success, but also ensures a better position at the job market. Fluent reading is a prerequisite for deeper comprehension, the ability to process complex information and well-developed critical thinking skills.

However, in recent years, there has been a change in the way people engage with information – there is a growing tendency for information to be perceived more visually and audibly, e.g. through podcasts, interactive platforms, or other multimedia sources, rather than through written texts. This trend has negatively affected students' reading habits and now they seem to be more likely to spend a couple of hours using their phones or other smart devices, instead of reading a chapter or two from an interesting book. They also tend to consider studying from traditional paper textbooks as something old-fashioned, outdated, and boring.

Schools should adapt to this changing landscape, since they are the institutions, which should equip students with the necessary skills and prepare them for the challenges of “real life”. Therefore, school teachers need to embrace innovations and try to implement them in their teaching practices – thus, making sure that they are adequate to the requirements of the contemporary world. They should meaningfully integrate digital resources and interactive technologies in lessons in order to engage their students' attention and to equip them with the necessary literacy and digital literacy skills.

The benefits of using visual aid in language teaching have long been acknowledged. The cognitive model of multimedia learning, presented by Mayer (2009) also indicates that combining text with “visual images of pictures and sound images of words” leads to better comprehension and retention of information. (Mayer, 2009, p. 62). Although there are numerous educational platforms, which can be used to enhance students' multimedia learning experience, the educational presentation software mozaBook and the online platform www.mozaweb.com seem to provide a complete range of resources at one place, such as 3D scenes, video and audio materials, test generating tools, and games, to name a few.

This paper presents the results of a pedagogical experiment, conducted with twenty-five eight-grade students from an innovative class from Yoan Ekzarh Balgarski Secondary School in Shumen, Bulgaria, which aimed to answer the research question: How do 3D scenes in mozaBook affect 8th-grade EFL learners' reading comprehension and classroom engagement?

Applying the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning in Foreign Language Teaching

Richard Mayer's idea that “people learn better from words and pictures than from words alone” forms the basis of his cognitive theory of multimedia learning (Mayer, 2009). He defines the term *multimedia instruction* as “the presentation of material using both words and pictures, with the intention of promoting learning”, where ‘words’ refer to verbal forms such as spoken or printed text, whereas ‘pictures’ refer to any pictorial form ranging from static images to videos and animations (Mayer, 2009, p. 5). In his book *Multimedia Learning*, the author suggests that when designing

multimedia resources, one should take into consideration how the human mind processes information, and introduces a cognitive model of how multimedia learning takes place. The model shows how information from multimedia presentations enters the sensory memory through the eyes and the ears and transforms into sounds and images into the working memory. There, these visual and auditory impressions are organized into *verbal* and *pictorial* models, facilitating the process of mentally connecting images and words. The new information is then integrated into long-term memory where it connects with prior knowledge and can be stored for later retrieval (Mayer, 2009, pp. 61-64).

Jane Crawford (2002) encourages the integration of an audio-visual component in foreign language classrooms, as multimedia materials “can create a learning environment that is rich in linguistic and cultural information about the target language” (Crawford, 2002, p. 85). She also believes that this provides both learners and educators with opportunities to explore the verbal, non-verbal and cultural aspect of the target language. In *Learning Teaching. The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching*, Jim Scrivener (2011) discusses the benefits of using various types of technological advancements, such as interactive boards, the Internet, multimedia and video materials in order to transform language lessons into an engaging learning experience. He provides inexperienced teachers with valuable advice on how to “make the difference between a slick video lesson and techno-muddle”, implying that technology in general and video materials in particular, should be used purposefully (Scrivener, 2011, pp. 376).

Moreno and Mayer (1999) discuss the cognitive principles of multimedia learning, highlighting the role of *contiguity* and *modality*. They suggest that effective multimedia design requires integrating text and graphics in close proximity in order to minimize excessive scanning, since separating these elements significantly impairs students’ learning. Based on the two experiments that they conduct, the authors conclude that “when designing instructional software” and educational resources, “it is crucial to physically integrate the corresponding graphic and text materials in a multimedia lesson” and that the materials presented should “allow for processing corresponding text and graphics in parallel” (Moreno and Mayer, 1999, p. 366).

The educational software mozaBook is designed in accordance with Mayer’s cognitive theory of multimedia learning, providing both teachers and students with opportunities to transform the foreign language

classroom into an engaging environment. mozaBook’s media library contains thousands of educational videos and 3D scenes offering a wide variety of functionalities, such as taking “a walk through the scene”, activating “text-to-speech function”, or generating exercises or board games at the click of a button (Mozaik Education Ltd., 2022).

Implementing 3D Learning for Reading Development

The experiment involved twenty-five 8th-grade students from an innovative class at Yoan Ekzarh Balgarski Secondary School in the town of Shumen, Bulgaria. The students’ English language proficiency ranges between A2 and B1 (with only one student at level C1, who is a native speaker). Most students have had prior exposure to technology-supported language lessons, which makes them more receptive to innovative and multimedia-based learning approaches. The experiment was carried out over two consecutive lessons (80 minutes altogether), allowing sufficient time for students to explore the 3D scenes, engage with the reading tasks, and participate in follow-up activities. The structure of the lesson session followed the effective lesson structure suggested by Richards and Lockhart (1996). According to it, lessons should begin “with a short review of previous, prerequisite learning”, followed by stating the goals, presenting the “new material in small steps, with student practice after each step”, teachers giving “clear and detailed instructions and explanations” for each stage, and providing “a high level of active practice for all students” (Richards & Lockhart, 1996, p. 113). Since the focus of the experiment is developing reading skills, it was taken into consideration that “the preferred approach to a reading text is top-down” – starting with gist reading (or skimming) and proceeding to reading for details (scanning) (Ivanova, 2017, p. 86).

In the first lesson, which lasted for 40 minutes, students were introduced to the megalithic structure of Stonehenge through a series of engaging activities designed to build their curiosity and enhance reading skills. The lesson began with a lead-in activity (Fig. 1) where students watched the 3D animation “*Megalithic Cultures in Europe*” on mozaBook (https://www.mozaweb.bg/Extra-3D_scenes-Megalithic_cultures_in_Europe-277393), featuring four different megalithic structures, including Stonehenge. Students then engaged in a brief discussion, imagining their sensory experiences at the site, which aimed to activate their prior knowledge and spark interest in the topic.

Fig. 1 Megalithic Cultures in Europe – lead-in activity

Next, students explored the 3D scene of Stonehenge on mozaBook (https://www.mozaweb.bg/Extra-3D_scenes-Stonehenge_Great_Britain_Bronze_-_12039), examining its structure, possible roles, and immersive time-travel features to provide a visual context.

Key vocabulary was then introduced through a matching activity both on the interactive board and on students' mozaWeb accounts, preparing learners for the reading tasks.

Fig. 2 Key vocabulary presentation

After that, students read the text quickly (skimming) to grasp its general idea, answering the guiding question: *What makes Stonehenge so unique and mysterious that it continues to fascinate people today?*

Then, students read the text again for details to complete a multiple-choice comprehension task (Fig. 3), followed by feedback and discussion, which helped to clarify misunderstandings, justify answers, and reinforce vocabulary in context.

Fig. 3 Reading for details – multiple-choice close activity

In the second lesson (which lasted for another 40 minutes), students were engaged in a series of activities designed to reinforce vocabulary and deepen their understanding of the history and purpose of Stonehenge through interactive and collaborative tasks. The lesson

began with a gapped text activity where students worked in pairs to complete sentences about Stonehenge using newly introduced vocabulary, followed by a sentence completion task to further contextualize and consolidate their understanding of some key terms.

Fig. 4 Topic-related vocabulary exercises

Next, students participated in a post-reading activity – a Stonehenge-themed board game created with the mozaBook built-in Board Games tool. Working in three

groups, learners applied their knowledge in an enjoyable and interactive format.

Fig. 5 Spin-the-wheel board game on mozaBook

This was followed by a whole-class discussion and reflection, where students shared their insights about Stonehenge and discussed how the 3D scene enhanced their comprehension. The lesson concluded with an anonymous attitude questionnaire designed to gather feedback on students' perceptions of learning with mozaBook 3D scenes, providing valuable insights into their engagement with this innovative approach.

Results and Insights from the Questionnaire

The survey results reveal a strong positive response to the use of 3D scenes in English language lessons. Twenty-five eight-grade students, aged 13-14, took part in the experiment and in the survey. The majority (80%) have been learning English for more than five years, which is a prerequisite for their good level

of language proficiency. At the beginning of the school year, they all took a placement test, revealing that seven students (28 %) were at language level A2, 68% were at language level B1-B2, and one student, a native speaker, was at language level C1.

The respondents rated 3D scenes as very interesting – 76% giving them a rating of 5 (on a scale of 1 to 5) and 24% rating them a 4. Students' engagement level was also high with 76% agreeing that the 3D scenes used in the lesson made it more engaging. Their positive attitude was further reflected in students' strong desire to continue using this 3D scene learning approach in future lessons, with 92% answering "Yes", and 8% – "Maybe" (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Students' strong desire to incorporate 3D scenes in English language classes

In terms of the impact of the 3D scenes on learning and understanding, 68% of the respondents reported that the 3D visualizations helped them understand the topic better, and 72% felt that the 3D scenes contributed to the development of their reading skills and to the improvement on their vocabulary. 80% agreed that they learned new information in English. Learners also found the 3D scenes useful for visualizing topics, with 84% agreeing that this is a way to provide a clearer understanding of difficult concepts.

With regard to motivation and enjoyment, 60% of the respondents felt highly motivated to learn English after the lesson session, and 56% admit that they had a lot of fun during the lessons. These results can serve as proof that 3D scenes can significantly increase motivation and enjoyment, which are key factors for academic success. When compared to traditional methods of learning, 68% of students stated that they prefer using 3D scenes to conventional approaches like textbooks. 64% felt that 3D scenes were more effective than traditional methods, indicating that technology-enhanced learning tools can have a significant impact on student engagement and on the overall lesson effectiveness.

When asked the open-ended question "What did you like most about using 3D scenes in English learning?", students' answers were quite positive, ranging from: "It's funny", "The 3Dness of it" and "It was interesting", to more detailed ones, such as "I like that it's different than a normal presentation.", "It was more interesting than a traditional lesson." and "I really liked how you could see and hear everything while reading – it made it feel super immersive. The virtual walk through Stonehenge in the 3D scene was awesome too

– it kind of felt like being in a video game, but the experience felt so real!".

Conclusion

The study demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating mozaBook's 3D scenes into foreign language lessons with regard to developing reading comprehension skills, enriching vocabulary, and increasing motivation. Incorporating 3D visualizations seems to be highly effective and engaging for students, since such multimedia instructional resources meet their expectations and prove to be a promising addition to modern educational practices. The findings from the conducted experiment highlight the potential of similar interactive learning tools in making foreign language learning more effective and appealing to students. In conclusion, mozaBook's 3D scenes offer a promising pathway to modernizing foreign language teaching and learning, equipping students with the necessary literacy and digital literacy skills to navigate the contemporary visual and interactive world. As modern technologies are entering educational practices worldwide, their potential to enhance learning outcomes and engage students in meaningful ways will only continue to grow.

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